

RESEARCH PAPER

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Work attitudes and needs of nurses: Their relationship

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the relationship between the work attitudes and the corresponding needs of the nurses in five (5) hospitals in the Province of Zamboanga Del Norte, Calendar Year 2016 - 2017. The descriptive method of research was used in the study. There were 43 respondents utilized. The main statistical tools were frequency count, percentage, weighted mean and spearman rho correlation. It was revealed that the respondent when analyzed were young adult, female, married, working as a staff nurse and are not continuing further studies. They served for 13 years or more, permanent and has been in her present position for 13 years and over. Further, it was revealed that they put more values on punctuality, good performance of tasks, commitment to work, ability to relate to different types of co-workers and good interpersonal relationships. They gave more importance to these beliefs rather than having a permanent position, work safety precautions beyond the basics, a candid communication culture and delegation of tasks. Though, these things were also important for them. They believed that they need all the aspects of professional and work skills development. The study revealed no significant relationship existed between the work attitudes and needs of the respondents. Hence, the needs of the nurses do not depend on their work attitude. To enhance the work attitudes and needs of the respondents a program is proposed partially giving additional benefits for the nurses; the management to conduct trainings on the identified training needs of the nurses in their respective hospitals; provide a standard manual of procedures and policies on infection control, assign nurses to different clinical areas of specialization and team building workshops among the hospital staff.

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Introduction

Nurses are among the most important hospital personnel. Their work covers a very large portion of the nurturing and healing process of patients. Their tasks generally require a lot of physical effort; their seriousness on the work was instinctively and substantially involves them mentally and psychologically. This makes human resource intervention for nurses' very critical (Stoner, 2007).

In the Philippines, hospitals rarely have specialized human resource development programs that focus on very specific needs of nurses. Usually, their personnel needs are seen from the administrative perspective in terms of salary, uniform, social security, and workplace safety and hygiene. Trainings are sometimes provided but are usually arranged with external providers who may lump them together, irrespective of specific situations in the workplace where they will later apply what they learned (Galvez-Tan, 2005).

The lack of focus to the specific needs of nurses is often due to a disjoint between their work attitudes and the perceived human resource intervention. To be fair, this neglected connection is also generally not taken into account in other fields, except in highly stable companies that invest heavily in human resource development. But this is changing. Slowly but surely, as more and more nurses go out of the country to work abroad, and the continuous brain-drain in the profession, a growing concern on the "quality" of nurses left behind, mostly inexperienced or unskilled. Hence, more and more hospitals and health institutions that employ nurses are investing in human resource, not only to correct the prevalent and growing inherent characteristic of their pool of encourage those who are already highly skilled and highly motivated to stay.

Indeed, this is the greatest challenge confronting Zamboanga Del Norte which has a relatively significant number of health institutions and hospitals. Its hospitals serve constituents not only from the Province but of neighbouring municipalities

as well, some of which do not have hospitals at all. The sheer volume of potential clients makes it imperative for hospitals here to continuously improve their pool of nurses. Not to mention of course is the measure of competition among private hospitals and the influence of public opinion for or against government hospitals.

Few studies have already been conducted along the needs of nurses in some hospitals in the Province but so far there is no study along the work attitudes and needs together being considered which is basically, the reason this study was undertaken.

The proponent of the present study is a nurse in an educational institution is also interested to dwell on the hospital settings. Hopefully, the study will help health institutions identify current needs of nurses as related to their work attitudes will be very helpful in maintaining the consistency of the health institution actual needs of field practitioners.

Materials and methods

This study utilized the descriptive method of research with the aid of a questionnaire checklist. This type of research collected data and defined or described some groups of phenomena and studied the relationship of the variables. The study gathered information about the work attitudes of nurses and their needs in the selected hospitals in the Province of Zamboanga del Norte. The study tested the hypothesis along the significant difference in the perceived needs of the respondents in the selected hospitals. Likewise, a correlational analysis was made to determine the relationship between the work attitudes and perceived needs of respondents.

There were five (5) selected hospitals involved in the study. Two (2) of them which are private and the other three (3) are public hospitals. The hospitals operations are in accordance with the standards of the Department of Health in the Republic of the Philippines. Of the five hospitals understudied, four hospitals are located in the city of Dipolog and one (1) is located in Dapitan City. These hospitals are made

accessible by both land and sea modes of transportation. There are four (4) major clinical services offered in these hospitals namely: Medicine, Surgery, Pediatrics and Obstetrics. Referrals from the nearby municipalities in the area aside from patients coming from the locality are provided with services they need. Hospital services include in and out-patient services, medical ancillary services. The Administrative, medical records and social services help facilitate nurses towards their duties and functions be studied so as development of programs for their enhancement in terms of performance be developed consequently will lead to increase productivity and quality of life and service.

It has been observed by the researcher, who herself is a nurse by profession that migration to foreign shores of nurses who have been working in the country's has continuously dropped the number of nursing professionals in the hospitals. Alarming from this event, apparently it shall not be surprising that out country in some future time, will be losing its own workers to some its people. But, before it takes its toll, interventions at this point in time shall be employed as response to the threatening situation.

The study utilized forty three respondents where three (3) or 6.97 percent of the respondents were Chief Nurses, two (2) or 4.65 percent of the respondents were Head Nurses and 38 or 88.38 percent of the respondents were staff nurses from the five (5) hospitals in Zamboanga Del Norte.

The main instrument used in gathering the data was a questionnaire-checklist which was supplemented by informal interviews and observations. The questionnaire was formulated and developed by the researcher with the help of the adviser. The questionnaire has three parts: part 1, dealt with the personal data about the respondents, the part 2, dealt with the perception of the respondents on their work attitudes along job security, work safety, punctuality at work, performance of tasks and assignments, commitment to assignments, openness of communication with co-workers, dealing with

strengths and weaknesses of co-workers, building rapport with co-workers and delegation of tasks. Part3, dealt with the perceived needs of the respondents using the given indicators.

Validation of the instrument

To find out whether the questionnaire can effectively measure the parameters under consideration, it was subjected to a validation process involving the 10 staff nurses from Piñan hospital which were not respondents of the study. During the validation, the respondents were requested to rate the questionnaire along qualities of clarity, organization, relevance to the research topic, freedom from assumption and conciseness using a five-point scale where 1 means "Strongly Disagree", 2 means "Disagree", 3 means "Neither Agree nor Disagree", 4 means "Agree" and 5 means "Strongly Agree". The answered questionnaires were evaluated and it was found out that all the questions were answered by the respondents and the data were tabulated and analyzed. Suggestions and recommendations were incorporated in the questionnaire. Upon the instruction of the researcher's adviser, the researcher proceeded to actual data collection.

Firstly, the researcher sent a letter to the Dean of the Graduate School, Jose Rizal Memorial State University, Main Campus, Dapitan City to seek an endorsement to field out the instrument of the study. The letter of the researcher together with the endorsement letter from the Dean was sent to the five (5) hospitals, one (1) to Dapitan City and four (4) to Dipolog City. Upon approval, the researcher then identified the respondents and personally administered the instrument to the respondents. Head nurses helped in the distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. In other hospitals, the researcher personally retrieved the accomplished questionnaire with the help of the nursing staff, One hundred percent retrieval rate of the questionnaire-instrument was achieved.

The data obtained were retrieved, arranged, classified and tabulated according to their statistical treatment. Ethical permission of the study was obtained from the Hospital Administrators of the five (5) hospitals. Prior to

the administration of the instrument the permission was obtained, the researcher informed the respondents that the participation in the study was voluntary and they were free to refuse to participate. Confidentiality was assured as no identifying information was included in the questionnaire.

Scoring procedure

To draw out the ratings of the respondents on their work attitudes, the Likert five-point scale was employed as follows.

Scale	Description	Interpretation
5	Strongly agree	Very positive
4	Agree	Positive
3	Neither agree nor disagree	Neutral
2	Disagree	Negative
1	Strongly disagree	Very negative

Scoring was done by multiplying ‘very important’ by 5; ‘important’ by 4; ‘moderately important’ by 3; ‘rarely important’ by 2 and not important by 1. Rating of the respondents as regard their needs, the Likert five-point scale was employed.

Scale	Description	Interpretation
5	Very important	Very high
4	Important	High
3	Moderately important	Moderate
2	Rarely important	Low
1	Not important	Very low

The responses were treated as raw data in this study. The data were tabulated, analyzed and interpreted carefully using the descriptive statistics. To quantify the interpretation of the data, the following statistical tools were used:

Frequency counting and percentage

This was used to determine the data on personal profile of the respondents, their perception of their work attitudes towards several indicators and their needs. This tool includes tallying the answers of the respondents.

Weighted mean

This was used to determine the quantitative units of the responses in the value scale. The verbal interpretation gave the corresponding description to the scale.

$$X = \{(F_1 \times X_1) + (F_2 \times X_2) + (F_3 \times X_3) + (F_4 \times X_4) + (F_5 \times X_5)\} / N$$

Where:

X = Weighted Mean (the final average score)

F = Frequency of each category (how often a response occurs in each scale)

X₁, X₂, X₃, X₄, X₅ = The values assigned to each category in the scale

N = Total number of responses (sum of frequencies: F₁+F₂+F₃+F₄+F₅)

The result of the weighted mean is not a whole number, so an option range was calculated so that the weighted mean can be categorized to the nearest hundredths. The option range was computed by subtracting the lowest from the highest and dividing the result by the number of scale, which is five.

Mean ranges	Equivalent	Interpretation
4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very positive
3.41-4.20	Agree	Positive
2.61-3.40	Neither agree nor disagree	Neutral
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Negative
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very negative

On the other hand, the option range for needs, its equivalent and verbal interpretation are as follows.

Mean Ranges	Equivalent	Interpretation
4.21-5.00	Very important	Very high
3.41-4.20	Important	High
2.61-3.40	Moderately important	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Rarely important	Low
1.00- 1.80	Not important	Very low

Spearman rank correlation coefficient or spearman rho

Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient (also known as Spearman's Rho or Spearman's Rank Order Correlation) is a non-parametric measure of the strength and direction of the association between two ranked variables. It evaluates how well the relationship between two variables can be described using a monotonic function. This was used to test the significant relationship of the demographic profile of the respondents to their work attitudes and needs. The formula for Spearman's Rho is:

$$\rho = 1 - \{6 \sum d^2 / (N(N^2 - 1))\}$$

Where:

ρ (Rho) = Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient.

d = The difference between the ranks of the corresponding values of the two variables.

N = The number of pairs (data points).

$\sum d^2$ / $\sum d^2 \sum d^2$ = The sum of the squared differences between the ranks of corresponding values.

Interpretation of Spearman's Rho:

$\rho = +1$: Perfect positive correlation (as one variable increases, the other increases).

$\rho = -1$: Perfect negative correlation (as one variable increases, the other decreases).

$\rho = 0$: No correlation (no monotonic relationship between the variables).

$0 < \rho < 1$: Positive correlation.

$-1 < \rho < 0$: Negative correlation.

Results

This chapter deals with the details of the findings of this study. It first presents the profile of the respondent nurses. It then delved on their work attitudes along job security, work safety, punctuality at work, performance of tasks and assignments, commitment to assignments, openness of communication with co-workers, dealing with strengths and weaknesses of co-workers and delegation of tasks. The needs of the respondents as to training and work security and safety were then discussed followed by a discussion on the relationship between the respondents work attitudes and needs. Finally, a plan of activities to address the attitudes and needs identified is proposed by the respondents.

Problem No. 1: What is the profile of the respondent-nurses in terms of the followings?

1. age;
2. sex;
3. civil status;
4. highest educational attainment;
5. length of service in the present position;
6. length of service in the organization;
7. present position; and
8. job status?

Age

Fig. 1 presents the age distribution of the respondents. As seen in the figure 30 to 69 percent of the respondents were 21 to 35 years old while the rest were belonged to the bracket of 36 to 55 years old. The mean age was 35.

The youngest respondent was 21 while the oldest was 51 years old. This means that the respondents are young adults. This sense of commitment, loyalty and hard-working. This finding support the view of Demrose in her article "Bringing across time".

Fig. 1. Profile of the respondents in terms of age

According to Sullivan, Nurses at this age becomes economically, intellectually, and emotionally self-sufficient. Chang (2007) further revealed that today's workplaces are generally engaged in by matured professionals.

Sex

Presented in Fig. 2 is the profile of the respondents in terms of sex. As shown in the figure, an overwhelming majority of the respondents, at 91 percent of the respondents were females while only a small portion of the respondents, at nine (9) percent were males. This means that nurses are predominantly female. This implies that the field is abounded by individual who care, who nurture, who ensure, who work harder and full of patience.

Fig. 2. Profile of the respondents in terms of sex

While it is a popular knowledge that nursing is a female-dominated profession the high percentage of employability of nurses made the males find their way to the nursing occupation. The finding is supported by population data in the country where female outnumber

the male a study of Reganon (2016). Moreover, many studies showed that nursing like teaching is a profession for females because of the nature of its work entailing tenacity and patience.

Moreover, the finding confirmed the prediction of sociologist Schaefer (2005) that the workforce by 2020 shall be increasingly composed of women. Men may benefit from their minority status through assumptions of enhanced leadership, by being given preferential treatment and being associated with a more careerist to work.

Civil status

The profile of respondents in terms of civil status is shown in Fig. 3. The figure reveals that more than half of the respondents (58 percent) were married while 17 or 40 percent were single and two (2) percent widowed. This means that most of the nurses working in five hospitals in Zamboanga Del Norte were married. This findings implies married nurses are tied with their families and so they prefer to stay in the Philippines because of their responsibility to their children and to the family's as a whole. This explains the very close relationship among members of the family.

Fig. 3. Profile of the respondents in terms of civil status

Highest educational attainment

The profile of respondents as to highest educational attainment is shown in Fig. 4. As reflected in the figure, 27 or 63 percent of the respondents were college graduates but did not pursue further education. The remaining 37% continued their post-graduate studies and distributed as follows: 13 or 30% have masteral units, two (2) or five (5) percent of the respondents are masteral graduates and one is pursuing doctoral degree. The data show that more than half of the respondents are quite satisfied with their basic qualification as nurses

considering the salaries they are receiving plus the benefits they enjoy though limited in the hospital. Nearly half of nurses with masteral units is a good indication that they are aiming for professional advancement, giving them confidence and competitiveness in the delivery of their services. It could be gleaned that professional advancement has not yet been given priority in the profession. Understandably, among the respondents who are relatively young but married.

Fig. 4. Profile of the respondents in terms of highest educational attainment

This finding is contradicted by Sergioivanni cited in Jacinto (2013) that professional development should not only be the personal concerned but by the office as well as they are also accountable to the clients. It cannot be overemphasized that professional development and advancement serves as the gateway to better options and more opportunities.

Length of service in the present position

Fig. 5 presents the distribution of the respondents according to the length of service in the present position. As shown in the figure, a 14 or 33 percent of the respondents have been in their present positions for just 11 months or less. Nearly another 14 or 33 percent of the respondents held there from one year to seven years. On the other hand, 15 or 35 percent have been in their positions for eight to 13 years and over. This means that respondents have varied years of experience ranging for less than 11 months to seven and 13 years and over. The finding implies that nurses in the field have differentiated abilities based on the year of exposure in the profession, some are experienced but others are inexperienced.

Fig. 5. Profile of the respondents in terms of length of service in the present position

Fig. 6 reflects the respondents by length of service in the organization. The figure shows that 16 respondents or 37 percent of the respondents have been in the service for 13 years or more. 11 or 26 percent served for 8 to 12 years, nine (9) or 21 percent have been working for 3 to 7 years while, one (1) respondent served for 1 to 2 years, and the remaining six (6) or 14 percent of the respondents were newly graduates. This means that a large number of the respondents have been engaged in the work for more than a decade. This implies that some sense of close relationship and orientation to work have been acquired by the respondents by the length of time they are in the organization.

Fig. 6. Profile of the respondents in terms of length of service in the organization

Present position

It can be gleaned in Fig. 7 the distribution of the respondents according to present position of respondents in the study. Majority of the nurse’s surveyed 31 respondents or 72 percent held the position of Nurse/Staff Nurse. Eight respondents or 19 percent were specialized field as OR Nurses, or were elevated to Nurse II or Head Nurses. Supervising Nurses, Chief Nurses and similar positions were held by less than a tenth (four or 9 percent) of them. The findings means that respondents understudy are new to their position as reflected to the rank by occupy, this implies that they are yet beginning to find themselves in the workplace.

Fig. 7. Profile of the respondents in terms of present position

Accordingly, McClelland as cited by Schane (2005) considered them as people with strong need for achievement, the kind who want to accomplish reasonably challenging goal through their own effort, money is weak motivators among these achievement oriented people. Other than achievement oriented, these are people with strong need for affiliation. The kind of person who want to have a positive relationships with others, they tend to project favorable image of themselves and take other steps to be liked by others. Moreover, high nAff actively supports others.

Fig. 8. Profile of the respondents in terms of job status

Job status

Fig. 8 presents the distribution of the respondents according to job status. Out of 38 nurses surveyed, 28 or 74 percent were permanent in their job. The rest of the respondents were distributed as follows: four (4) or 11 percent were, contractual; another four (4) or 11 percent were casual employees and two (2) or five (5) percent worked as volunteer nurses. The data indicate that majority of the nurses are permanent in their work. This means that the typical respondent is a young adult, female, married, has not pursued further education, a staff nurse and has worked for 13 years. This finding implies that at their stage in life, they are more or less stable financially and are

secured in their work; therefore, there is strong job security that may tie them in their workplace.

Problem No. 2: How do the respondents' rate the work attitudes of the staff nurses along?

1. Job security;
2. work safety;
3. punctuality at work;
4. performance of tasks and assignments;
5. commitment to assignments;
6. openness of communication with co-workers;
7. dealing with strengths and weaknesses of co-workers;
8. building rapport with co-workers; and
9. delegation of tasks?

Attitudes can have a significant effect on the behavior of a person at work. The world of work is concerned with attitudes towards supervision, pay, benefits, promotion or anything that might trigger positive or negative reactions. Employee satisfaction and attitudes represent one of the key areas of measuring organizational effectiveness.

This section considers the role of workplace attitudes in influencing important organizational outcomes and the methods organization use to develop these attitudes in their workers.

Job security

Table 1 shows the level of agreement to the statement manifesting the respondents work attitude along job security. The respondents strongly agreed with items 1 and 2 wherein job security is important to hospital employees which obtained an average value of 4.91 and individual recognition for above standard performance means a lot to employees which obtained an average value of 4.58 both are described as strongly agree. Respondents agreed with items 3 and 4 with wage increase to be given to employees who do their job well and that hospital is a good place to work. Both obtained an average value of 3.7 which described as agree; and moderately agreed on Satisfaction with the amount of compensation given by their hospital which obtained an average value of 3.02.

Table 1. Perception on job security

Indicator	Average value	Descriptive equivalent	Interpretation
Job security is important to hospital employees.	4.91	Strongly agree	Very positive
Individual recognition for above standard performance means a lot to employees	4.58	Strongly agree	Very positive
Wage increase should be given to employees who do their job very well.	3.7	Agree	Positive
This hospital is a good place to work	3.7	Agree	Positive
I am satisfied with the amount of compensation given to me in this hospital	3.02	Moderately agree	Neutral
Mean	3.98	Agree	Positive

Table 2. Perception on work safety

Indicator	Average value	Descriptive equivalent	Interpretation
I feel safe while caring my patient	3.98	Agree	Positive
Medical errors are handled appropriately in the hospital	3.98	Agree	Positive
Nurses are at high risk for exposure to blood-borne pathogens due to increase in percentages of seriously ill patients and patients with infectious diseases	3.88	Agree	Positive
A confidential reporting system that documents medical incidents is helpful for improving patient safety	4.51	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
I hesitate to use a reporting system that documents medical incidents because I am concerned about being identified	3.02	Moderately Agree	Neutral
Mean	3.87	Agree	Positive

These findings imply that the respondents have positive work attitude on Job security because they

are enjoying their job. This confirmed by Helliot (2010) who stated that having security in the job

would result to positive attitude towards works because it boost one's morale and satisfies all other needs. It encourages commitment and loyalty. However, he added the satisfaction declines when downsizing of workers occur.

Work safety

As shown in Table 2, the respondents strongly agreed on a confidential reporting system that documents medical incidents is helpful for improving patient safety it obtained and average value of 4.51 which describes as strongly agree; while they agreed with items 1 and 2 that if ever they were the patient they will feel safe being treated in the hospital, medical errors are handled appropriately in the hospital with

average value of 3.98, and that nurses are at high risk for exposure to blood-borne pathogens due to increase in percentages of seriously ill patients and patients with infectious diseases with average value of 3.88; and the respondents moderately agreed with, they hesitate to use a reporting system for medical incidents because they are concerned about being identified with average value of 3.02.

These findings indicate that despite the hazard of working in the hospital means of undue exposure to certain hazards, like nosocomial infection, radiation, or even violent patient with mental disorder, the nurses are satisfied with hospital security and have also positive attitude on Work Safety.

Table 3. Perception on punctuality at work

Indicator	Average value	Descriptive equivalent	Interpretation
I am punctual in reporting for duty, no undue absences nor under time	4.37	strongly agree	Very positive
Coming to work on time shows my respect to my superiors, peers, subordinates and patients	4.56	strongly agree	Very positive
I see to it that I come on time despite personal inconveniences	4.4	strongly agree	Very positive
I routinely show up to work as scheduled	4.57	strongly agree	Very positive
Punctuality is important, expected and appreciated	4.64	strongly agree	Very positive
Mean	4.50	strongly agree	Very positive

Table 4. Perception on performance of tasks and assignments

Indicator	Average value	Descriptive equivalent	Interpretation
Excelling in every task/assignment is a normal thing for me	4.19	Agree	Positive
I am willing to learn new tasks and assignments outside my specific field of expertise	4.86	Strongly agree	Very positive
A nurse should performed his/her duty with utmost respect for life	4.8	Strongly agree	Very positive
A nurse should discharge from his/her duty after completing the task	4.76	Strongly agree	Very positive
I feel I am working too hard on my job	3.98	Agree	Positive
Mean	4.52	Strongly agree	Very positive

Punctuality at work

Table 3 presents that the respondents strongly agreed on all indicators along punctuality at work, such as being punctual in reporting for duty, no undue absences nor under time with an average value of 4.37, coming to work on time shows their respect to their superiors, peers, subordinates and patients with an average value of 4.56, also coming on time despite of personal inconveniences with an average value of 4.4, showing up to work as scheduled with an average

value of 4.57, and punctuality is important, expected and appreciated with an average value of 4.64. These findings suggest that the respondents have a very positive attitude on Punctuality at Work. Studies revealed that, high levels of job involvement have been found to be related to fewer absences and lower resignation rates and it measures the degree to which a person identifies psychologically with his or her job and considers his or her performance level important to self-worth.

Table 5. Perception on commitment to assignment

Indicator	Average value	Descriptive equivalent	Interpretation
I am highly motivated and hardworking	4.19	Agree	Positive
Pride in one's work is actually an important reward	4.29	Strongly agree	Very positive
I do not leave a task/assignment unless it is finished or attained	4.31	Strongly agree	Very positive
I try to overcome obstacles that hinder completion of an assignment	4.43	Strongly agree	Very positive
Where exigency of service so required, I am willing to render service beyond the normal number of hours I work in the hospital	4.36	Strongly agree	Very positive
Mean	4.31	Strongly agree	Very positive

Table 6. Openness of communication with co-workers

Indicator	Average value	Descriptive equivalent	Interpretation
Important issues are well communicated at shift changes	4.17	Agree	Positive
There is good communication between nursing section and other sections in the institution	4.05	Agree	Positive
Information obtained through incident report is used to make patient care safer in this hospital	4.31	Strongly agree	Very positive
Communication breakdowns which leads to delays in delivery of care are common	3.93	Agree	Positive
It is easy for nurses in the hospital to ask questions.	4.38	Strongly agree	Very positive
Mean	4.17	Agree	Positive

Performance of tasks and assignments

Table 4 presents the level of agreement of respondents along performance tasks and assignment. Items 2,3 and 4 were strongly agreed by respondents, that they are willing to learn new tasks and assignment outside their specific field of expertise which obtained an average value of 4.86, they should perform their duty with utmost respect for life obtained an average value of 4.8, and they should discharge their duty humanely with conscience and dignity obtained an average value of 4.76, while they agree with excelling in every task/assignment is a normal thing for them 4.19, and they feel they are working too hard on their job obtained an average value of 3.98. Items 1 and 5 were described as agreed.

These findings imply that the respondents work attitude towards performance of task and assignments is very positive and they achieve high satisfaction from their work.

Commitment to assignments

Table 5 presents the level of agreement of respondents along commitment on assignment. Majority of the respondents strongly agreed with

the following: pride in one's work is actually an important reward obtained an average value of 4.29, they don't leave a task/assignment unless it is finished obtained an average value of 4.31, they try to overcome obstacles that hinder completion of an assignment obtained an average value of 4.43, and where exigency of service required, they are willing to render service beyond and the respondents only agreed with they are highly motivated and hardworking obtained an average value of 4.19.

These findings show that the respondents have a very positive attitude on commitment to assignments. This confirms the statement of Robbins (2008) that job attitude is original commitment and high job involvement means identifying with one's specific job, while organizational commitment means identifying with one's employing organization.

Openness of communication with co-workers

Among the five (5) indicators in Table 6 the respondents agreed with the following: important issues are well communicated at shift changes, average value of 4.1, there's a good communication between nursing section and other sections in the institution, average value of

4.05, and that communication breakdowns which lead to delays in delivery of care are common, average value of 3.93, they strongly agreed with information obtained through incident reports used to make patient care safer in their hospital, average value of 4.31 and it's easy for nurses in the hospital to ask questions when there is something they do not understand, with an average value of 4.38.

These findings indicate that nurses have positive attitude on openness of communication with co-workers. According to Homans as cited in Martines (2006), greeting each other pleasantly is an example of a behavior emerging from good working relationships thus promoting openness of communication will lead to efficiency on the job.

Dealing with strengths and weaknesses of co-workers

The respondents strongly agreed on all indicators of Table 7 on dealing with strengths and weaknesses of co-workers such as they appreciate the skills, talents and knowledge of their co-workers, average value of 4.48, they accept the weaknesses of their co-workers and can live with them without diminishing their capacity to work with them, average value of 4.21, the physicians, nurses and other hospital staff work together as well coordinated team, average value of 4.52, they respect the decision of supervisors and other members of team and can effectively interact with others in performing their daily duties in the hospital have both obtained an average value of 4.45.

Table 7. Perception on dealing with strength and weaknesses of co-workers

Indicator	Average value	Descriptive equivalent	Interpretation
I appreciate the skills, talents and knowledge of my co-workers	4.48	Strongly agree	Very positive
I accept the weaknesses of my co-workers and live with them without diminishing my capacity to work with them	4.21	Strongly agree	Very positive
The physicians, nurses and other hospital staff work together as well as coordinated team	4.52	Strongly agree	Very positive
I respect the decision of superiors and other members of team	4.45	Strongly agree	Very positive
I can effectively interact with others in performing my daily duties in the hospital	4.45	Strongly agree	Very positive
Mean	4.42	Strongly agree	Very positive

Table 8. Perception on building rapport with co-workers

Indicator	Average value	Descriptive equivalent	Interpretation
I personally know all my co-workers and am able to relate with them as individuals	4.38	Strongly agree	Very positive
I maintain a friendly relationship with all my co-workers	4.48	Strongly agree	Very positive
Working in this hospital is like being part of a large family	4.43	Strongly agree	Very positive
Disagreements in this hospital are appropriately resolved (i.e not who is right but what is best for the patients)	4.07	Agree	Positive
The quality of relationship in the informal work groups is quite important	4.43	Strongly agree	Very positive
Mean	4.36	Strongly agree	Very positive

This means that nurses in the hospital of Zamboanga del Norte have a very positive attitude in dealing with strengths and weaknesses of co-workers and between the administrator and employees, this implies that there is an environment that promote cooperation, sharing and feeling of belonging which motivate people to work productively. Accordingly, they are people with high need of affiliation they are people satisfied with their job and workplace. This finding is

corroborated by Rajab *et al.* (2012) that regardless of one's capability and ability, the employees were satisfied with the help extended by their co-employees along their work.

Building rapport with co-workers

Table 8 shows that majority of the respondents strongly agreed with almost all items except item 4 they personally know their co-workers and able to

relate with them as individuals, average value of 4.38, they maintain a friendly relationship with their co-workers, average value of 4.48, working in their hospital is being a part of a large family. Item 3 and 5 which refers to their work in the hospital is like being in a large family and there quality of

relationship in the informal work group is quite important with an average value of 4.43, and they agreed with disagreements in their hospital are appropriately resolved (i.e. not who is right but what is best for the patient) with an average value 4.07.

Table 9. Perception on delegation of tasks

Indicator	Average value	Descriptive equivalent	Interpretation
My co-workers/subordinates can generally be trusted to complete tasks or assignments with minimum supervision	4.14	Agree	Positive
I generally delegate task/assignments that my co-worker/subordinates are equipped to handle	4.17	Agree	Positive
Briefing personnel before the start of the shift is an important part of patient safety	4.57	Strongly agree	Very positive
Sometimes I feel that I have too many bosses who tell me conflicting things	3.83	Agree	Positive
I feel that I am supervised more closely than I need and want to be	3.43	Agree	Positive
Mean	4.03	Agree	Positive
Grand Mean	4.24	Strongly agree	Very positive

These findings indicate that the respondents have a very positive work attitude on building rapport with co-workers. This supports Maslow's cited by Velasco (2016) that people displayed strong group tendencies as shown in their practices of "we" syndrome, smooth interpersonal relationships and togetherness, the fourth level need in his 5 level needs involves esteem and status includes ones feeling of self-worth and competence, the feeling of competence is assurance of others. In some point it is still very close to self-actualization. Basically, the fourth need is satisfied that afford them to feel secured.

Delegation of tasks

Along the five (5) indicators of Table 9 on delegation of tasks the respondents agreed on the following: their co-workers/subordinates can generally be trusted to complete tasks or assignments with minimum supervision, average value of 4.14, they generally delegate tasks or assignments that their co-workers/subordinates are equipped to handle, average value of 4.17, sometime they feel that they have too many bosses who tell them conflicting things, average value of 3.83 and they feel that they are supervised more closely than they need and want to be, average value of 3.43 the respondents strongly

agreed with briefing personnel before the start of the shift is an important part of patient safety, average value of 4.57.

The findings means that the respondents believe that the need to train and develop staff nurses who desire greater opportunities and challenges in their work. This implies a positive work attitude on delegation of tasks.

Problem No. 3: What are the needs of the respondents along the given indicators?

Needs of the respondents

What do employees need in order to excel? It is a pleasant environment, an appreciative manager or motivation? While these things are important, the key ingredient shared by all successful employees is confidence. Confidence comes from ability, and results in productivity. Employees who have the skills and knowledge needed to perform their duties and whose accomplishments are recognized will out-produce; both in quality and quantity, employees who are uncertain are struggling with their assigned job tasks. Since confidence begins with competence, it follows that employee training is a crucial component in molding a productive work force.

Table 10. Perceived needs of the respondents

Indicator	Average value	Descriptive equivalent	Interpretation
Job security			
Orientation on labor laws relevant to the job	4.73	Very high	1
In-service education programs for staff in the hospital	4.68	Very high	2
Pursuit of graduate or postgraduate studies	4.44	Very high	4
Training in skills outside the immediate skills requirements of present job/position	4.46	Very high	3
Mean	4.58	Very high	
Work safety			
Current situation of nosocomial infections and predisposing factors in the hospital and information on infection control policies and procedures	4.56	Very high	1
Provide health-care workers with better education regarding the types of patient care activities that can result in hand contamination and cross-transmission of microorganisms	4.51	Very high	2
Training on how to prepare occurrence/accident reports which can be used for risk assessment and loss protection	4.49	Very high	3
Fire drill and other training in response to workplace hazards and accidents like earthquakes, etc.	4.44	Very high	4
Mean	4.50	Very high	
Punctuality at Work			
Time management	4.66	Very high	2
Work Ethics and Values	4.76	Very high	1
More flexible working hours	4.34	Very high	4
Greater freedom in arranging for day-off and holidays	4.37	Very high	3
Mean	4.53	Very high	
Performance of Tasks and assignments			
Disease and conditions	4.59	Very high	1.5
How to conduct assessment and diagnosis	4.59	Very high	1.5
Basic Computer skills training and internet	4.27	Very high	4
Stress Management	4.56	Very high	3
Mean	4.50	Very high	
Commitment to assignments			
Use and maintenance of work tools and equipment	4.56	Very high	2
Clinical placements away from the normal place of work	4.20	High	4
Mental health and promotion and prevention	4.46	Very high	3
Current best practices in clinical skills	4.61	Very high	1
Mean	4.46	Very high	
Openness of communication with co-workers			
Interpersonal relationships and teamwork	4.44	Very high	2
Interpersonal communication skills	4.46	Very high	1
Electronic communication skills	4.12	High	3.5
Use of multimedia facilities	4.12	High	3.5
Mean	4.29	Very high	
Dealing with strengths and weaknesses of co-workers			
Intervention skills (e.g management of violence and aggression)	4.34	Very high	3
Therapeutic skills	4.51	Very high	1.5
Multidisciplinary training so that I learn from colleagues with different backgrounds and expertise	4.27	Very high	3
Participatory teaching/training skills	4.51	Very high	1.5
Mean	4.41	Very high	
Building rapport with co-workers			
Team building and values of each individual's role in delivering highest quality care to patient	4.54	Very high	1
Peer-teaching on non-job hobbies skills	4.22	Very high	4
Conflict resolution	4.34	Very high	2
Filipino values for team effectiveness	4.29	Very high	3
Mean	4.35	Very high	
Delegation of tasks			
Leadership training including coaching/mentoring	3.34	Very high	4

Management training for nurses with supervisory position	4.42	Very high	3
Quality improvement and assurance strategies	4.52	Very high	2
Risk management	4.57	Very high	1
Mean	4.21	Very high	

This study also tackled on the needs of the respondents in the workplace. The respondents were interviewed on the degree of importance of the training classified under the nine (9) categories. The results are summarized in Table 10.

The table reveals that the overall need for all the needs items listed were very high, with all of the need categories yielding very high need. This indicates that the perceived needs of the respondents on the individual training needs listed ranged only from high to very high in significant number of cases. This implies that the respondents felt that they need all the aspects of professional and work skills development enumerated.

As to specific training needs, almost all items registered very high perceived need. Three items, namely, additional clinical assignments away from normal place of work, electronic communication skills, and use of multimedia facilities, however were rated only as high by the respondents. This indicates that extra training works, training on electronic communication such as e-mail, chat or video conferencing and use of multi-media facilities (LCD projector, computers, etc.), although deemed important by the respondents were not seen as important as the other items. This implies that the respondents do not consider these training critical in their present workplace. Job-related trainings are more important to the respondents since they can immediately apply these new acquire knowledge and skills in their actual work.

By category on labor laws relevant to the job, in-service education programs for staff in the hospital, pursuit of graduate or postgraduate studies, training in skills outside the immediate skills requirements of present job/position, and current situation of nosocomial infections and predisposing factors in the hospital and information on infection control policies

and procedures were among those that received the highest ratings from respondents. This indicates that the most needed trainings by the nurses-respondents were varied including those relating to the legal aspects of their profession, in-house profession-related updates, graduate and post-graduate trainings on other fields that will allow them to diversity of skills. This implies that the most-needed human resource needs of the respondents do not only dwell on the profession-related concerns but also on the holistic career development and self-improvement.

Problem No. 4: Is there a significant relationship between respondent's work attitudes and needs?

Table 11 presents a summary of the computations of relationship between work attitudes and needs of the respondents. This shows the results of the test of relationships between the work attitudes and the needs of the respondents. The computed t-value is 0.32 which denotes a positive relationship between the work attitudes and needs of the respondents. However, the computed value is less than the tabular value of .786 at .05 level of significance. Therefore, there is no significant correlation between the two variables. This could lead to the idea that the needs of the respondents do not depend on their work attitudes.

According to Kreitner (2005) the best way to increase performance is to improve job satisfaction and that needs arise because of unmet expectations. The findings of the study is supported by Kreitner in the book *Organizational Behavior* which reported that to anticipate the needs the best way is to increase workforce satisfaction so that productivity of employees is not hampered such confirmed Herzberg contention, that satisfaction leads to high performance. Thus, it appears that managers can positively affect performance by increasing employee's job satisfaction.

Table 11. Relationship between work attitude and needs of the respondents

Aspects	Work attitudes		Needs	
	X	Rank	X	Rank
Job security	3.98	8	4.58	1
Work safety	3.87	9	4.50	3.5
Punctuality at work	4.50	2	4.53	2
Performance of tasks and assignments	4.52	1	4.50	3.5
Commitment to assignments	4.31	5	4.46	5
Openness of communication with co-workers	4.17	6	4.29	8
Dealing with strengths & weaknesses of co-workers	4.42	3	4.41	6
Building rapport with co-workers	4.36	4	4.35	7
Delegation of tasks	4.03	7	4.21	9

Conclusion

Based on these findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The typical nurse respondent is 35 years old, female, married, working as a staff nurse and does not continue further studies, has served for 13 years or more, permanent and has been in her present position for 13 years and over.
2. The respondents put more values on punctuality, good performance of tasks, commitment to work, ability to relate to different types of co-workers and good interpersonal relationships than other indicators. They tend to give more importance to these beliefs rather than having a permanent position, work safety precautions beyond the basics, a candid communication culture and delegation of tasks, and although they consider these things are also important for them.
3. The respondents believed that they need all the aspects of professional and work skills development enumerated.
4. The needs of the respondents do not depend on their work attitudes.
5. The following programs are proposed to enhance the work attitudes and needs of the respondents: additional benefits for the nurses; the management to conduct trainings on the identified training needs of the nurses in their respective hospitals; provide a standard manual of procedures and policies on infection control, assign nurses to different clinical areas of specialization and team building workshop among hospital staff.

References

Arines MO. The Nursing Care Competencies and Work Behavior of Staff Nurses.

Armstrong-Stassen M. Human resource management strategies and the retention of employees.

Attitudes Journal of Vocational Behavior. Retrieved on May 11, 2016, from <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/entrez/>

Baloloy VG. 2001. Congruency of the Training and Organization Behavior of Employees.

Behavior at Work. 11th ed., New York: McGraw-Hill/Irwin.

Behavior in Organizations. 2nd ed., Manila, Philippines: National Book Store.

Behavior: Basis for Educational Management Review. Unpublished.

Best-Run Companies. New York: Warner Books.

Bohrstedt GW, Knoke D. 2008. Statistics for Social Data Analysis.

Borromeo AB. 2008. Partnership in Nursing Education Towards Improved Health Care.

Camarines Sur Polytechnic College. Nursing Education Studies.

Carbo S. 2008. Social Services in West Visayas. Published by MT West Visayas State University.

Care in Catanduanes Government Hospital. Master Thesis, Aquinas University.

- Chang CC.** 2007. Evaluating the effects of competency-based web learning on self-directed learning aptitudes. *Journal of Computers in Mathematics and Science Teaching* **26**(3), 197–216.
- Cohen MZ, Sarter B.** 2002. Love and Work: Oncology Nurses' View of the Meaning of Care.
- Dionesia A, Buenafe.** 2008. Quality Nursing Education Towards Effective Nursing Practice. Dissertation. Jose Rizal Memorial State University.
- Fielding J, Weaver SM.** 2004. A comparison of hospital and community-based nursing. *Journal for Advanced Nursing*.
- Foley BJ, Kee CC, Minick P, Harvey SS, Jennings BM.** 2002. Characteristics of nurses in public and private hospitals. *Nursing Practice Newsette* 30(January-June).
- Gifford BD, Zammuto RF, Goodman EA.** 2002. The relationship between hospital unit climate and outcomes. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*.
- Gillies De Ann.** 2004. *Nursing Management: A Systems Approach*. 3rd ed. Philadelphia, PA.
- Hall TL.** 2002. Why Plan for Human Resources for Health? Discussion Paper.
- Helliot P.** 2010. *Human Resource Management*. Monterey Brooks Incorporated.
- Hongoro C, McPake B.** 2004. How to bridge human resource gaps in health. *The Lancet* 364(October).
- Implication to the Nursing Service.** 2000. Master's Thesis. Camarines Sur Polytechnic Colleges.
- Ingersoll GL, Olsan T, Drew-Cates J, DeVinney BC, Davies J.** 2002. Nurses' job satisfaction and outcomes. *Journal of Nursing Administration*.
- Jacinto M.** 2013. School-Based Management in Relation to Teachers' Job Satisfaction.
- Khurshid K, Merchant RJ, Hirani D.** 2005. Registered nurses' job satisfaction in public hospitals.
- Kim H, Sr. Esther Young HFS.** 2004. Interpersonal relationships between healthcare professionals and nursing outcomes.
- Knoop R.** 2005. Relationships among job involvement, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment. *Journal of Occupational Psychology*.
- Kozier B, Erb G, Blais K, Wilkerson JM, Van Leuven K.** 2008. *Fundamentals of Nursing Practice*.
- Krausz M, Sagie A, Bidermann Y.** 2005. Actual and Preferred Organizational Commitment for Nurses. *Journal of Psychology*.
- Kreitner R.** 2005. *Organizational Behavior*. Irwin Incorporated, USA.
- Lagasca EM.** 2001. The Values, Work Attitudes, and Job Satisfaction of Nurses in Private and Public Sectors. Master's Thesis.
- Luba M.** Forecasting models for human resources in health care. *Journal of Nursing Administration*.
- Martines CR, Fule GS.** 2000. Management of Human Medical and Nursing Staff at the Bicol Medical Center. Master's Thesis. Camarines Sur Polytechnic Colleges.
- Michel DL.** 2005. A Nursing Perspective on Cancer Supportive Care.
- Milkovich GT, Boudreau JW.** 2004. *Human Resource Management*.
- Monge LA.** 2002. The Relationship Between Holistic and Therapeutic Care. Master's Thesis.

- Newstrom JW, Davis K.** 2002. Organizational Behavior: Human Behavior at Work.
- Nieswiadomy RM.** 2004. Foundations of Nursing Research. 4th ed. Pearson.
- O'Brien-Pallas L, Baumann A, Donner G, Murphy GT, Lochhaas-Gerlach J.** 2001. Older RNs and Their Work. Canadian Journal of Nursing Leadership.
- Obalesco AC, Lim JB.** 2001. Nurse Performance and Quality Patient Care. Philippine Journal of Nursing 64(1): January-March.
- Pacis EG.** 2001. Nurses' Assessments of the Management Practices. Master's Thesis. Jose Rizal Memorial State University.
- Pervin LA, John OP.** 2001. Theory and Research. 8th ed. New York: Harper Collins.
- Peter T, Waterman RJ.** In Search of Excellence: Lessons from America's Best-Run Companies.
- Poster EC, Ryan J.** 2004. A Multiregional Study of Nurses' Beliefs and Attitudes. Journal of Nursing Management 13(1): January.
- Purseley A, Luker K.** 2005. Attitudes and stereotypes: Nurses' work with older people. Journal of Advanced Nursing.
- Rajab A., Panatik SA, Abdul Rahman H, Shaari R.** 2012. Managing Quality Support Staff in a Higher Learning Institution. Paper presented at the 2012 International Conference on Education and Management Innovation, Singapore.
- Reganon G.** 2016. Administrators' leadership practices in relation to nursing services.
- Reodica CN.** 2007. Collaborative roles of community health. Master's Thesis.
- Robbins SB.** 2008. Organizational behavior: Values, attitudes, and job satisfaction. 8th ed. New Jersey: Pearson Education Asia Pte Ltd.
- Schaefer R.** 2005. Sociology. McGraw-Hill Incorporated, New York, USA.
- Shader K, Broome ME, Broome CD.** 2001. Satisfaction, organizational commitment, and career intent. Journal of Nursing Administration.
- Stoner J, Wankel C.** 2007. Management. 3rd ed. New Jersey: Prentice-Hall.
- Swansburg RC, Swansburg RJ.** 2009. Introductory management and leadership for nurses.
- Thompson P, Kholi K.** 2007. Health promotion training needs analysis: An integral approach. Health Care Management Review.
- Tumulty G, Jernigan IE, Kohut GF.** 2009. The work attitudes of full-time and part-time registered nurses. Health Care Management Review.
- Velasco V.** 2011. Teachers' development practices in relation to educational outcomes. Wesley Longman.
- West ME, Nash M.** Factors influencing satisfaction and anticipated turnover for nurses in an academic medical center. Journal for Nursing Administration, April issue.
- Zulueta F, Costales NEB.** 2003. Methods of research.